

Technology, Health and Awareness: A Sociological study on Burdwan Town

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Abstract

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Technology, health and awareness are very much associated with each other. We live in a post-modern world and modern technologies play an important role. In my research I have shown that how in Burdwan town different types of modern technological equipment are associated with health and provide us awareness and care.

Keywords: technology, internet, gadgets.

Introduction

Health is wealth. Physically and mentally fit people do their work sincerely and spread happiness within family and among others. On the other hand Technology¹ is an essential part of modern living. We start our morning with technology and before we go to bed still technology stay with us. Majority people of our society are very much aware about their health and always they are trying to take care of their health. Now it is very easy because in market we find so many technological gadgets² and machines and by the use of those technological gadgets people can easily conduct virtual visits to doctors, nurses and caregivers. Among all technological gadgets there are some famous that is cell phones³, tablets and laptops etc. They can also easily get information about medicine and symptoms of diseases by the use of online search

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¹ *Technology is the scientific knowledge dealing with the applied sciences.*

² *A gadget is a small mechanical and electronic device.*

³ *A small telephone that people can take with them and use outside their homes. A cell phone requires a subscription to a service provider and requires either a prepaid or monthly billing setup. Generally, they have more functions than traditional land lines and need to be charged after a period of time, also called mobile phone or mobile device.*

engine such as Google⁴ through the Internet. New technologies provide people with primary care at home; it seems that there is further potential for getting more benefits by using relevant medical technologies. Indeed those have the power to improve individual and public health transforming the quality of health care and reducing the cost of health care services. It can give patients and citizens more control over their health and well-being, reduce the administrative burdens for care professionals, and support the development of new medicines and treatments, for instance.

Modern societies are based on technology. Making people aware about health is very easy. High quality medicines, modern medical equipment's, modern internet based communication, etc. are day by day improving and changing the nature and definition of health and awareness. People can easily check their primary health oriented issues at their home by using electronic gadgets. Information about health, viz., such as blood pressure, body weight, calorie, body temperature etc. is getting available at their home by a click on the mouse. To give a specific example, by the use of 'Bremed Digital Blood Pressure Monitors' we can check our blood pressure anywhere. Technology is also aiding to take care of mental stress, anxiety, mental health and many other problems of health. Technology must play a central role for proposed health care reform to contain costs, improve access, and save lives.

Review of Literature

A lot of work has been done in the field of Medical technology. Here I present a brief review of the literature .A literature review serves certain essential functions of research. Firstly, a literature review shows that the researcher is aware of the existing work already undertaken in the area. Secondly, it identifies what the researcher takes to be the key issues, the crucial questions and the obvious gaps in the available knowledge. Thirdly, it provides signposts to the researcher about 'where

⁴ *Google is a search engine through which people can get information on World Wide Web.*

the research is coming from' and what theories and principles have shaped the present research. (Denscombe, 1999, p. 158) Among those who have contributed to the field, a few may be mentioned. All these studies have concentrated on information technology or e health. Among them are Mcdaniel, who has drawn our attention to advances in information technology in relation to health⁵, Clercq, who has studied e health⁶, Fett⁷, who studied the relationship between technology and health care, Burney, Aquil and Mohammed⁸, who studied the relationship between technology and health care with special reference to developing countries, and Jerome, who studied the impact of technology on quality and cost of medical care⁹.

Through Review of literature we got much information about health relation with technology and efficient care. But these studies are based on western countries and their economy was strong. But my study area is based on Burdwan town of West Bengal.

Objectives of the Research

⁵ Mcdaniel G. J, 2009, *Advances in Information Technology and Communication in Health*, IOS Press, Netherlands.

⁶ Clercq, D. E, 2008, *Collaborative Patient Centric E-health*, IOS Press, Netherlands

⁷ Dr. Fett M, 2000, *Technology, Health and Health Care*, Volume – 5, Commonwealth Department of Health and Aged Care, Australia.

⁸ Burney S. M. Aqil, Mahmood N, Abbas Z, July 2010, "Information and Communication Technology in Healthcare Management Systems: Prospects for Developing Countries", *International Journal of Computer Applications*, Volume – 4.

⁹ Wang K. Jerome, "Systematic Review: Impact of Health Information Technology on Quality, Efficiency, and Costs of Medical Care", *Research Gate*.

Through this research I wanted to focus on frequent use of technological gadgets by people of Burdwan town and their relationship with health awareness. How do people of Burdwan town getting information about health and how they maintain their health care? And also the knowledge of technological gadgets and there implication on human life to justify care and awareness. In my survey I wanted to focus on two types of people firstly; who are the permanent residence of Burdwan town and secondly; migrant people who are coming into here for any of their health related assistance.

Method of Study

To do this research I collected primary data as well as secondary data. I did survey which was based on survey method. The social survey is a research strategy. (Denscombe, 1999, p. 7) Interviews and questionnaires are the main methods adopted for doing the survey. My sample size was 120 and I collected all those samples randomly. After pilot survey I prefer Burdwan town of Burdwan district for my survey area. It is one of the famous districts in West Bengal. Health facilities and health care centers in Burdwan town are growing very fast. I collected data from different places of Burdwan town, such as Khosbagan, Station bazaar, Baburbag, Ullas, and Burdwan Hospital. I also sent email to different people of Burdwan. Khosbagan is one of the famous places where more than thousands of doctors and pathological centers are present. Different types of people from different areas are going over there.

Relationship among Technology, Health and Awareness

Technology and health are very much associated with each other. Technology helps people from different ways. People are using different tools to enable them to manage their own health conditions and/or care and support arrangements, getting information, advice, peer

support etc. Every time people are becoming dependable on techno gadgets. From morning to night we are frequently associated with different technologies, among maximum of them are frequently associated with health. Here I used different parameters to showing that how technology and health are very much inter-connected to each other.

Information technology has made significant contributions to our world, namely in the medical industry. With the increased use of electronic medical records (EMR), tele-health services, and mobile technologies like tablets and smart phones, physicians and patients are both seeing the benefits that these new medical technologies are bringing radical changes in different field of technology.

Computer Technology and Mobile Gadgets

Now day's computers¹⁰ are a necessary part of life of every literate people. It provides us multi-dimensional way for communication. Not just communication it connects every associated parts of our society which have enormous impact on health and awareness. Modern society is based on digital process and those are the primary gadgets which are forcing people to be a part of those gadgets and change the behaviour. Computer technology has developed to the point that a literate person can operate computers, though the purpose and uses are different for everyone. People can use desktop or laptop or go to cyber-cafes for using computers. Computers provide us all information which we wanted to getting just we

need an internet connection. Through computer we can easily communicate with doctors, websites of many hospitals and nursing-homes etc. Computers provide us big screen and fast data processing. On the other hand mobiles are useful gadgets through which people can do many works those as well as same works which they are also doing through computer. When multi functioned smart phone was not in the market then we have only features phone and through that features mobile phone people are done only two works that was calling and messaging. But the times are changed now; it is time to smart phones and different types of gadgets. Now calling and messaging are not the only functions of smart phones, it is doing so many things. Entire information of global world just in our finger tips. Apart from different qualities and work of smart phones I am just focusing on how health issues associated with mobile phones. My first important fact is communication. Not just communication it provide us many useful things. It changed the traditional nature of communication. Through mobile phone people can easily communicate with doctors, their visiting hours, consult with doctors or experts about diseases, and also getting information about medicine too. But some cases internet plays important role. Medical technology has evolved from introducing doctors to new equipment to use inside private practices and hospitals to connecting patients and doctors thousands of miles away through telecommunications. It is not uncommon in today's world for patients to hold video conferences with physicians to save time and money normally spent on traveling to another geographic location or send health information instantaneously to any specialist or doctor in the world. Here I displayed a picture of laptop, tables and mobile gadgets through which I tried to showing technological uniformity.

¹⁰ A programmable electronic device designed to accept data, perform prescribed mathematical and logical operations at high speed, and display the results of these operations. Mainframes, desktop and laptop computers, tablets, and smartphones are some of the different types of computers. Compare analog computer, digital computer.

Picture: 1 Laptop, Tablet & mobile (Source: Internet)

With more and more hospitals and practices using medical technology like mobile devices on the job, physicians can now have access to any type of information they need from drug information, research and studies, patient history or records, and more within mere seconds. And, with the ability to effortlessly carry these mobile devices around with them throughout the day, they are never far from the information they need. Websites of different hospitals, institutes and medical centers help people to getting information about different health problems and their available treatments. People can ask about their problems and get answers from different experts online. Respondents said that through they don't have sufficient contacts of doctors and medical centers or hospitals but to finding them those gadgets helps them very well. In Burdwan town, 97% people are using their mobile phone to communicate with health centers, hospitals and doctors. They using their mobile phones to find out the location of doctors chambers and also it helps people to getting appointment with different doctors.

Mass Media and Health Awareness

Media plays important role to provide health awareness among people. Since the last decade, media has playing a major role to promote awareness about health. The media — everything from television, radio, and film to games, advertising, and social media outlets like Facebook and Twitter — can have significant impacts on individual and population health. Exposure to media, especially among youth, may affect health behaviors such as substance use, sexual activity, and eating habits. In modern society media has

comes into many different formats, including print media (like books, magazines, and newspapers).

Newspapers, magazines, news etc. provide people health tips, awareness among fitness and figure, provide information about new launch medicines and also their effects on human. Different types of diseases, how they spread and their effected areas as well as medicines which will solve those problems -- all those information we can achieve through media technology.

Impact of Social Media on Health Sector

Now social media is a basic part of life. Maximum teenage spend their lots of time with Facebook, whats app, YouTube and many other social applications. Always they tried to find something. It might be educational matters or information about health. Most of the boys wanted to know how to create muscular body, how to lose extra fat, how to make slim etc. On the other hand maximum people are aware about positive and negative qualities of foods and most of the time they are getting that information through Facebook. Girls are very much aware about their skin, beauty, and figure. They are getting all those beauty products from different online stores; such as Flipkart, amazon, etc. In my survey I had met many teenagers who are concerned about their health, and tried to maintain to their fitness in regular basis. Here I displayed a combined picture of different social medium which are very popular for communication.

Picture: 2

Different Social Medias ,like Facebook, Whats app,Twitter, We Chat etc. (Source: Internet)

Medi-claim and health are related to each other. Now most of the people have their medi-claim, which help them at the time of health problems and they are admitted into hospitals or nursing homes. Now through computer and mobile application we are getting information about different medi-claim websites and about their policies. Through social media people are checking health websites and blogs. It is very easy to them because they can easily tag, post and share valuable and useful websites, blogs and so many things. 70% people said that when they are spending time to checking Facebook then so many health tips, about new medicines they are getting easily due to tag and liking many health pages. People of Burdwan area, who are flexible in social media, are easily aware about health related issues and information' which they are getting from Facebook and other social media.

Television and Health Awareness

Television plays a big role to entertainment. But apart from entertainment we are getting many useful things which are necessary related to health. Now many television channels telecast different health related programs and advertisement. Many programs provide information about nutritional diet, healthy foods, yoga, fitness exercise, and many more things. Common awareness advertisement about health is "cigarettes smoking causes cancer", through movies, serials, advertisements television inform us about the effects of cigarette smoking. Through news channels we are getting updated about different diseases, newly emerged medicines, hospitals, facilities and so many things. Health insurances are necessary for everyone; through television we are aware about those things. Because due to heavy health related costs it is very difficult to common people to taking care about their health problems.

At the time of survey I had seen people of middle age are very much calculative about daily

health checkup cost, doctors' fees, and costs of medicines. By the use of technology they manage all those things.

Techno based Medical Equipment

Medical technology is a broad field where innovation plays a crucial role in sustaining health. Areas like biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, information technology, modern medical devices and equipment, and more have all made significant contributions to improving the health of people all around the world. In the healthcare industry, the dependence on medical technology cannot be overstated, and as a result of the development of these brilliant innovations, healthcare practitioners can continue to find ways to improve their practice – from better diagnosis, surgical procedures, and improved patient care.

Health measure tools and gadgets

Nowadays so many gadgets are invented through which we can measure our health issues at own home. Blood pressure, rate of pulse, body weight, level of nutrition etc. we can measure all those things through electronic gadgets at our own home. From "small" innovations like adhesive bandages and ankle braces, to larger, more complex technologies like MRI machines, artificial organs, and robotic prosthetic limbs, technology has undoubtedly made an incredible impact on medicine. "Accu-Chek Diabetes Care" is a blood sugar meters, lancing devices, insulin pumps, and diabetes testing supplies to help people to manage their blood sugar levels. "Fit-bit" accurately tracks all-day stats like steps taken, distance travelled, calories burned, stairs climbed, and active minutes. "Omron HN-286 Digital Weight Scale" through we can measure our weights. In my survey I have noticed that 14% people use health measure tools and gadgets at their home. Now days so many health care gadgets and mobile applications we can find easily in the market and virtual mobile stores. Those type of gadgets making conscious-ness about health constantly in our society.

People are very much concern about their health and they do maintain checkup their health regular basis. And now every hospital tried to maintain the records of their all patients, this process is called 'Electronic Medical Records'. An electronic medical record is a digital and portable version of the current paper file system that would be accessible to all doctors. That means whenever you see a new physician, you could stop filling out endless paper forms, as your doctor could access everything about you on the computer. Improving quality of life is one of the main benefits of integrating new innovations into medicine. Medical technologies, like minimally-invasive surgeries, better monitoring systems, and more comfortable scanning equipment are allowing patients to spend less time in recovery and more time enjoying a healthy life.

Survey Results

My survey area was Burdwan town which I already mentioned. Last 5 years scenario on health awareness and health care in Burdwan town is totally change. We all know that television is a very important tool for the promotional and educational components of national programmes. In India, television reaches a large audience, and those shows which are well-targeted, researched, pre-tested, and adequately placed in the broadcast schedule become attractive, competitive and cost-effective ways to communicate new and time-tested advice. It reaches those people who do not come to health facilities. Before I telling about the findings I wanted to showing how different age group people spending their time in television.

Different age group watching television
(Source: Field data)

The total number of respondents in this survey was 120 and I collected data from different age groups. Here I divided all respondents into three different age clusters for evaluating their viewpoints regarding television. In Fig1 I represent vertically the total number of respondents and horizontally represent different age group division.

Here we found those people whose age groups are 11 – 30 among them 33.33 % people are watching television. Here I wanted to show that these groups are basically teenagers and they love to watching movies, serials, cricket and so many things which will provide them entertainment. In Burdwan town this age group people are giving importance on those programs and advertisements which will provide them information that how they to control their diet, how to maintaining physique and also varieties of information about taking care of their bodies. They are basically young groups and they all are watching television. They told me that television provides them awareness about various sectors and also about health related issues, such as awareness about AIDS¹¹ diseases, information on

Figure: 1

¹¹ Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) is a spectrum of conditions caused by infection with the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV).

Polio¹² vaccination and solution of Tuberculosis (TB)¹³ Heart Diseases, and so forth. Advertisement and serials are important media of television through which people are getting this type of information.

We all know that people are very busy in their life and daily schedule, but when they are free at home they are spending their time watching television. There are in the 31 – 50 age group, people who are busy with their works and daily schedules. Television is a medium to getting information. Through television people tried to shape their behaviour and sometime maintain a proper schedule to watching fixed. programmes. Television provides us various options of channels and programmes. In Burdwan town 41.67 % of middle age people spend their time watching television and they love to watch serials, and cinemas. Most of them are house wives and they spend a lot of time in serials. Among them few are aware of watching some news and programs which are related to health. People of middle age, basically males, are busy with their work, and maximum women are house wives who love to watch television.

Ages 51 – 70. It is the crucial age group when people are facing some health problems though in all cases it is not applicable. But at this age people tried to know about health, awareness and medium to getting health care facilities. They have the information about best hospitals, and doctors of Burdwan. Television is the best medium through which they are getting maximum information. They said that through local channels they are getting useful healthcare related information easily. As well as information about minor health issues, newly launched medicines

¹² Polio (poliomyelitis) is a highly infectious disease caused by a virus. It invades the nervous system and can cause irreversible paralysis in a matter of hours.

¹³ Tuberculosis (TB) is caused by a bacterium called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The bacteria usually attack the lungs, but TB bacteria can attack any part of the body such as the kidney, spine, and brain. If not treated properly, TB disease can be fatal.

and healthcare products such as paracetamol¹⁴, volini gel¹⁵ etc., which people can get easily in the local medicine stores. Television is not just a medium. It is a platform for gaining knowledge or entertainment. So, how we use it depends upon us..

Burdwan is a large district as well as one of the famous town of West Bengal where medical facilities are very good apart from all others places. Nowadays so many local regional cable channels are flourishing in Burdwan town and they are providing people relevant information. People are getting information about nursing-homes, doctors and their chambers, medicine shops through those local cable channels, advertisements and different types of health related programs which are very relevant and useful. In this survey I found that people are watching television and somehow they are aware and conscious about general health issues and preventive care of those issues. On the other hand youth are basically aware about some modern health gadgets such as Accu-Chek¹⁶, Fitbit¹⁷ etc. as well as they also know highly technology based modern macro machine, like MRI¹⁸ technology

¹⁴ Paracetamol (acetaminophen) is a pain reliever and a fever reducer. Paracetamol is used to treat many conditions such as headache, muscle aches, arthritis, backache, toothaches, colds, and fevers. It relieves pain in mild arthritis but has no effect on the underlying inflammation and swelling of the joint.

¹⁵ Volini is a modern day pain reliever, scientifically formulated for effective pain relief.

¹⁶ Accu-Chek is a blood glucose monitoring systems; lancing devices, test strips, and diabetes management software which help empower people with diabetes to live their lives to the fullest.

¹⁷ Fitbit is an activity tracker and wireless-enabled wearable technology devices that measure data such as the number of steps walked, quality of sleep, steps climbed, and other personal metrics.

¹⁸ Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a test that uses a magnetic field and pulses of radio wave energy to make pictures of organs and structures inside the body. In many cases, MRI gives different information about structures in the body than can be seen with an X-ray, ultrasound, or computed tomography (CT) scan. MRI also may show problems that cannot be seen with other imaging methods.

and multi specialist hospitals; such as 'Camri' and 'Saranya' etc.

On the other hand mobiles are very useful gadgets. Nowadays, every person has a mobile phone and maximum of them have smartphones¹⁹. Apart from call and text messages through mobile they can do so many things. Figure 2 shows the uses of mobile phones among different age groups.

Figure 2

Uses of mobile Phones in Different Groups (Source: Field data)

Here I divided all respondents into three age groups because different age for different reasons. This figure shows that 31.67 % persons have their own mobile phone. In my survey I find that teenagers are very much dependable on their mobiles and them spending lots of time with their mobile. Facebook, Whatsapp, Hike, webchat etc. are modern means of communication. Through those applications they always connect with family, friends and other people. They told me that

¹⁹ A smartphone is a mobile phone with an advanced mobile operating system which combines features of a personal computer operating system with other features useful for mobile or handheld use. They typically combine the features of a cell phone with those of other popular mobile devices, such as personal digital assistant (PDA), media player and GPS navigation unit. Most smartphones can access the Internet, have a touchscreen user interface, with either an LCD, OLED, AMOLED, LED or similar screen, can run third-party apps, music players and are camera phones. Most smartphones produced from 2012 onwards also have high-speed mobile broadband 4G LTE internet, motion sensors, and mobile payment. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Smartphone>

now for every health related information, queries about medicines and diseases they can get through virtually by the use of Internet. Google is the biggest search engine. On the other hand, basically girls are always wants to become beautiful, wants to fit, always worried about losing extra fat, etc.. Through social media , like Facebook, blogs it is very easy for them to getting information regularly at their fingertips.

Apart from teenagers, people in the 31 – 50 age group also have their own phone. In my survey their percentage was 32.5 %. But their uses of mobile are very much different from teenagers. They are not spending their lots of time time with mobile phones as like teenagers are doing. But they are aware about healthcare. In Burdwan town I noticed that maximum people of this age group people tried to communicate with the doctors and caregivers by the use of voice calling. They are nor depending on smartphones or any kind of smart applications. Only voice calling and few times through text they tried to maintain communication with doctors, care givers, nursing homes, medicine shops and many other places. But among this age group some peoples are aware and flexible with smartphones and other types of communications. People, who are in the profession of medical representative are very much informative about health. Through mobile they can easily get all data, information about medicine and diseases, knowledge about health policies and new inventions. Among 51 – 70 age groups people are not well versed about using mobile phones. Through re-socialization most of them learned how to make voice calls and sometime texted to others. Among them, 29.17 % people use mobile phone and it is the only medium through which they communicate with doctors and get information about health. It is obvious that mobile gadgets and healthcare has a strong relationship, but it is differs from person to person.. Here I wanted to showing different functions of a smartphone. Firstly, it is the only portable instrument which we can carry and communicate with doctors or others in our home or any other places. People whose are reside in Burdwan town and whose are coming from outside the Burdwan town both have one common

thing that is they fixed their appointment with doctors by voice calling. Here the main thing is when they are outside the home then mobile is the only medium of communication. Secondly, among the young people, mobile is an essential part of life. They are very much techno centric. Through healthy related application they got information about health. Apart from chatting and texting when they are facing health problems then they tried to find out solution through the Internet. They follow many health blogs, videos and messages which are helpful to them. Thirdly, so many application are invented which are specified focusing on health issues. Here I wanted to tell some famous health related application that is health tracker, S Health, Pedometer, Yoga, BMI Calculator, Women's Home Fitness, and Periods Tracker etc.

Apart from mobile gadgets computers are also playing a major role in healthcare. In this survey I noticed that hospitals and nursing homes cannot be maintained properly if computer is not there. The computer has become an important support tool for healthcare professionals. Hospital information systems employ computers in various ways to deal with the vast amount of information used by various departments. In my survey people told me that now healthcare is very much computer based. Computerized equipment's like MRI technology made a revolutionary impact in the field of health care industry. People are now going to those hospitals and nursing homes where modern health technologies are available. People felt that modern technology based health care is better than those without modern technology.

Conclusion

It is very easy to conclude that technology and health are very much associated with each other. In my survey 99% people said that they frequently associated technology with health related issues. Young people; through mobiles and tablets, regularly check up lists of healthy foods for their good skin, tips for slim figure, suggestions for losing their fat and so many things. On the other hand those people who cannot use Internet and mobile application frequently, through call and messages tried to maintain the contacts with doctors and health centers. People are buying

health gadgets through which they can measure their routine health checkup at their home. All those things are very easy to us to getting by the technological development. Highly specified and newly invented technology in medical science provides people so many facilities and accuracy of diagnosis and treatment of diseases. Medical scientists and physicians are constantly conducting research and testing new procedures to help prevent, diagnose, and cure diseases as well as developing new drugs and medicines that can lessen symptoms or treat ailments.

Through the use of technology in medical research, scientists have been able to examine diseases on a cellular level and produce antibodies against them. These vaccines against life-threatening diseases like malaria, polio, MMR, and more prevent the spread of disease and save thousands of lives all around the globe. In fact, the World Health Organization estimates that vaccines save about 3 million lives per year, and prevent millions of others from contracting deadly viruses and diseases.

Technological innovations in the healthcare industry continue to provide physicians with new ways to improve the quality of care delivered to their patients and improve the state of global healthcare. Through technology's integration with areas like disease prevention, surgical procedures, better access to information, and medical telecommunications, the medical industry and patients around the world continue to benefit.

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